

UTILISATION OF ANDAMAN RESIN. PART I

BY NRIPENDRA CH. SAHA AND A. N. SAHA

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT, UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA

(Received March 29, 1955)

The resin obtained from *Canarium euphallum* (Andaman resin) has been examined with a view to its utilisation as a varnish constituent. The resin is characterised by low ash content, low acid value, high m.p., medium hardness and high bulking value, indicative of its use as a very good quality varnish constituent. Its solubility in oils and in many organic solvents offers a wide choice of solvents, diluents and thinners.

The resin under investigation is obtained from *Canarium euphallum*, belonging to Burseraceae family. This tree frequents deciduous forests in Andaman islands. Other trees of this family, namely, *C. luzonicum* and *C. commune* habitate island of Luzon and India respectively and yield oleo-resins.

The natural commercial product is light yellow to very dark brown in colour, fragile and has little odour. The resin contains both vegetable and inorganic impurities. When purified by dissolving in ethyl ether and filtering to remove vegetable remains, dirt and dust, it exhibits physical and chemical properties, as shown in Table I

TABLE I

Physical properties :		Chemical properties :	
Colour	... Brownish	Direct acid value	... 25
Odour	... Slight resinous odour	Sapon. value	... 25.5
M. P.	... 130°	Iodine value	... 55.9 (Wijs)
Sp. gr.	... 1.0 (30°)	Ash content	... 0.71%
Solubility	... Soluble in ethyl ether,	Colour reactions :	
	benzene, toluene, xylene like ethylmethyl ketone, acetone, ethyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, cellosolve.	Halphen-Hicks ⁵	... Light violet, very slowly deepens in colour.
Bulking value	0.110 gallon/lb.	Liebermann-Storch ⁴	... Dark red (immediate) and red-brown (after 12 mins.).
		Heat reactivity	... Non-reactive.

On steam distillation it yields 2.3% essential oil which exhibits the properties, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Odour	... Resinous	Acid value	... 96.0
Colour	... A very faint greenish yellow	Av. M. W.	... 255.8 (cryoscopic)
Sp. gr.	... 0.905 at 30°	Ref. index	... 1.4955 at 30°
		$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	... 3°

Melting point.—It was determined by Durrans' method¹ modified by Rangaswami¹. The method consists in heating 0.2 g. of the sample to melt in a porcelain crucible of about 17 c.c. capacity. The molten resin is allowed to cool to room temperature when the mass of resin is covered with 100 g. of mercury. A thermometer is introduced in the mercury bath which is heated slowly at the rate of about 2° to 4° per minute. The temperature at which the first bit of resin appears on the surface of the mercury is reported as the M. P.

Solubility of resin.—A known weight of powdered resin was shaken thoroughly with a known weight of solvent in a well-stoppered conical flask in a shaking machine and allowed to settle overnight. A weighed quantity of the filtered solution was then taken in a tared glass basin, the solvent evaporated off, and the resulting resin was weighed.

TABLE III

Solvent.	Solubility. (w/w)	Solvent.	Solubility (w/w).
Chloroform	17.90%	Benzene	40.28%
Acetone	5.90	95% Ethyl alcohol	5.85
Amyl alcohol	9.06	Amyl acetate	8.53
Butyl acetate	6.40	Petroleum ether (60°-80°)	60.5

Bulking value.—Bulking value³ was determined by adding known amounts of resin in 100 c.c. of the solvent (amyl acetate) in a graduated cylinder. The resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight and then the increase in volume due to resin addition and the insoluble deposition was recorded.

TABLE IV

Resin added to 100 c.c. amyl acetate.	Increase in volume.	Bulking value or volume bulked in gallon/lb. resin.	Mean bulking value.
.1 g.	0.85 c.c.	0.103	...
3	2.7	...	0.110 gallon/lb.
4	3.78	0.112	
5	4.75	0.114	
8	7.55	0.113	

Heat reactivity.—Heat reactivity of the resin was determined by noting the gelation time of tung oil according to the method of Brown⁵. Tung oil or tung-resin (5 c.c.) was placed in a special test tube which with its content was placed in a bath at 293°. The temperature of the bath was decreased to 282° within two minutes of placing of the test tube. At this temperature the bath was kept as steady as possible. When the sample had been in the bath for 9 min. a glass rod (kept in the test tube) was raised at intervals of 15 sec. Time was noted when the sample became firmly set.

TABLE V

Tung oil (%)	Resin (%)	Time of gelation.
100	0	14 min. 36 sec.
90	10	15 14
80	20	15 54
70	30	16 30

The results show that with the addition of Andaman resin the time of gelation is retarded, proving that the resin is heat-inactive.

Natural resins, which are generally used in the manufacture of spirit and oil varnishes, enamels and lacquers, have properties akin to Andaman resin. Thus, it may be possible to utilise this resin in the manufacture of vehicles of varnishes, enamels and lacquers. So experiments were carried out to compare the varnishes made from Andaman, phenolics and Congo copal resins.

Preparation of varnishes.—Since the resin is soluble in oil there is no necessity of running. The resin was heated to 300° when heated linseed stand oil (4.8 poise) was added to it and the resulting mixture was cooked at 300° till the desired stringiness developed. The cook was cooled to 100° and was thinned with the thinner. A copal and a modified phenolic resin varnish were prepared under similar conditions. In case of copal, a previously run sample was used. A sample of modified phenolics was dissolved in hot oil and was cooked. The composition of the varnish is as : resin 25.0 g., linseed stand oil (4.8 poise) 50.0 g., Pb-linolenate 3.5 g., Co-linolenate 0.5 g. and thinner, 84.0 g. and 90 parts mineral spirit and 10 parts Indian turpentine.

*Compatibility of resin.*⁷—Run copal or phenolics (10 g.) was melted and kept at 204.4° when equal amount of powdered *canarium* resin was sprinkled over the melt in small amounts within 10 minutes. The mixture of the two resins was poured into a metal container and made into a thin cake. The cold ~~part~~ was found clear with run copal as well as with modified phenolics.

*Drying time.*⁸—Thin films of the varnish were applied on glass slides and their drying times were observed at room temperatures and at 120° in an oven. The film was reported as dried when there was no tackiness on touching.

*Resistance to cold water.*⁸—Varnish films on glass slides were dried for 72 hours at room temperature and a portion of each of them was immersed in water. Failure to water was reported when the film failed to return to its original colour within 5 minutes after exposure to air.

*Resistance to boiling water.*⁸—The test was done in boiling water in exactly the same way as in cold water resistance test. Failure by the first appearance of blisters in the boiling water was also noted.

Resistance to 5% NaOH.—Procedure was the same as with cold water resistance excepting that the films before examined were washed with distilled water.

Hardness.—Hardness was determined by lead pencil method.

TABLE VI

Varnish sample.	Drying time at room 100° temp.		Resistance to water.		Relative hardness.	Resistant to 5% NaOH.
	hrs.	hrs.	4 Days in cold water.	1/2 hr. in boiling water.		
100% copal	19.0	2.00	Resistant	Resistant	5	Resistant for 12 min.
100% Andaman resin	20.0	2.25	„	Non-resistant, very slightly blistered	4	„ 8
100% Modified phenolics	17.0	1.88	Non-resistant, slightly whitened	Resistant	3	„ 10
{ 20% Andaman { 80% Copal	19.25	2.00	Resistant	„	Between 4 & 5	„ 11
{ 50% Andaman { 50% Copal	18.40	2.03	„	„	Do	„ 10
{ 70% Andaman { 30% Copal	19.75	2.15	„	„	Do	„ 9
{ 20% Andaman { 80% phenolics	17.25	1.90	Non-resistant, slightly whitened	„	3 & 4	„ 10
{ 40% Andaman { 60% phenolics	17.50	1.90	Do	„	Do	„ 9
{ 50% Andaman { 50% phenolics	18.00	2.0	Resistant	„	Do	„ 9
{ 60% Andaman { 40% phenolics	18.75	2.1	„	Non-resistant, slightly whitened	Do	„ 8

DISCUSSION

Low ash content, high melting point, medium hardness and high bulking value of the resin are indicative of its use as a very good varnish constituent. As the resin has a low acid value, it does not require any chemical modification.

The resin is soluble in oils and appreciably soluble in many organic solvents such as hydrocarbons, esters, alcohols and ethers; hence, the varnish made with this resin will have a wide choice of solvents, diluents and thinners.

As it is compatible with other natural as well as synthetic resins, it can be used along with other resins.

The comparison of qualities of varnishes made with this resin and the other two, namely Congo copal and modified phenolics, shows that (a) Andaman*

varnish takes a longer time to dry; (b) is resistant to cold as well as boiling water like the other two varnishes; (c) is slightly less resistant to 5% NaOH solution than phenolic varnish; (d) gives a film of intermediate hardness. By blending this resin-varnish with the other two varnishes some of its properties can be modified for useful purposes.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Durrans & Rangaewami, *J. Oil Col. Chem. Assoc.*, 1929, 12, 173 /1930, 13, 287.
2. Mantell, "Technology of Natural Resins," John Wiley, 1942. p. 101.
3. *Ibid.*, p. 89.
4. Liebermann & Storch, *Ber.*, 1884 17, 1884; *Ber. Osterr. Ges. Chem. Ind.*, 1887, 9, 93.
5. Hicks, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1911, 3, 86.
6. Shuey, *ibid.*, 1940, 32, 921.
7. Mantell, Ref. No, 2, p. 153.
8. Turkington *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 1935, 27, 1321.